

ISSUES THAT INFLUENCE IMPLEMENTATION OF STRATEGIC PLANS IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS – A CASE OF GARISSA COUNTY, KENYA

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Abstract:

Strategic planning has been used in schools in developed countries leading to school improvement. Strategic planning can help an organization to clarify future direction, to establish priorities, to diversify its products or services and to deal effectively with rapidly changing circumstances. The study was conducted in Garissa County and sought to find out issues that influence implementation of strategic plans in public secondary schools in the County. Despite the evidence of the existence of strategic plans in most of the public secondary schools, the concern has been failure by institutions to implement them. The purpose of the study was to establish issues that influence implementation of strategic plans in public secondary schools in Garissa County. The target population for the study were school principals, BoG members and teachers in public secondary schools in Garissa County. Stratified random sampling techniques and census methods were used at various stages of the research process. The study focused on independent variables such as leadership quality, resource allocation, stakeholder involvement, human resources capacity and school culture. The respondents were 22 school Principals, 22 Teachers and 25 BoG members. The instruments of the study were questionnaires in which both open and closed ended questionnaires were used. The data collected was analyzed using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) utilizing descriptive statistics such as frequency table and graphs. The study found that the implementation of strategic plans in schools is faced with a number of challenges that include lack of funds, political interference and to some extent, security. Of these challenges, lack of funds is the most prevalent. Further, most schools depend on school fees and government grants as the only source of revenue. The study therefore recommends that schools should diversify on their sources of finance so that they do not only rely on fees and government grants, but can also generate funds through other income generating activities.

Keywords: strategy implementation, strategic plans, strategy implementation key issues

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1. Introduction

The study was conducted in Garissa County and aims to establish issues that influence implementation of strategic plans. A strategy is a set of activities or processes that an organization intends to use in order to achieve its set goals and aims (Pearce, 2009). Strategic plan is an organization's process of defining its strategy or direction, and making decisions on allocating its resources to pursue this strategy, including its capital and people. Wernham (2004) observes that in a strategic planning process, resources such as people, skills, facilities and money to implement the strategy must be adequate. Some governments have made it compulsory for schools to formulate strategic plans in line with national strategic plans, for example in Australia the government has a guideline of what schools should include in their strategic plan (State of Victoria, 2010) and United Kingdom have passed the 1998 Education Reform Act which gave the responsibility to develop strategic planning for schools (Giles, 1995).

The term strategy implementation is simply used to refer to the actions an organization takes to meet its strategic goals. According to MOE (2006-2011), successful implementation of strategic plans was expected to improve efficiency in resource allocation, improve the quality of education provided to Kenyans, while also addressing equity and gender imbalance, improve the learning environment for boys and girls, including those with disabilities and special needs. In order for the Government to achieve this, it was a ministerial requirement that public organizations like secondary schools implement strategic plans.

Despite the importance of good strategic plan the Kenya government have put in place policies and guidelines on strategic planning in public secondary schools, very few schools have adopted it (Achoka 2007). It is upon this background that this study investigated the issues that influence implementation of strategic plans in public secondary schools in Garissa County.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

The study establishes issues that influence implementation of strategic plans in public secondary schools, a case of Garissa County. A strategy is a set of activities or processes that an organization intends to use in order to achieve its set goals and aims (Pearce, 2009). Research has shown that strategic planning is one of the major steps that schools can take to address the problems they face in enhancing the quality of their programmes in provision of Education (Bell, 2002). It is for this reason that the ministry of education through the Sessional Paper No.1 of (2005) mandated all managers of educational institutions in Kenya to develop strategic plans for managing their institutions. On the same note Ministry of education in its strategic plan (2006-2011) made compulsory for all public secondary schools to develop strategic plans with aim of enhancing result based management and efficiency in their operations. However, many studies carried out to determine the level of implementation and impact of strategic plans indicated dismal result. A report by Yara and Wanjohi (2011) indicated that the performance of the Kenyan secondary schools in national examinations has

been deteriorating thus revealing a wide gap in the strategic plan implementation. This can be attested to the recent escalation of public protests concerning poor performance in secondary schools which is a reflection of schools' inability to provide services that meet learners and stakeholders' expectations. This cast some doubts on the extent of implementation of strategic plans in secondary schools, especially in Garissa County which is rated among the poorly performing counties in the national examination.

According to a survey on Kenya Education Management on Capacity Assessment which was carried out by Research Transparency International (RTI) and East African Education Consultant in (2007) strategic plans in public schools are not fully implemented. The quality of education cannot be achieved and sustained if the resources and facilities are not available in sufficient quality and quantity (Ngware, Wamukuru and Odebero, 2006)

A survey by Ngware et al. (2006) showed that over 60% of schools in the country do not have strategic plans, though currently some schools have developed the plans they are slow in implementation of the same. This means that majority of public secondary schools in Kenya of which Garissa County is inclusive do not implement strategic plans. The researcher was encouraged to undertake the study after having discussions with the teaching profession who noted that most schools in Garissa County did not implement their strategic plans. It was on the basis of this background that the study aimed to fill this gap by investigating the issues that influence implementation of strategic plans in public secondary schools in Garissa County.

1.3 General Objective

To establish issues that influence implementation of strategic plans in public secondary schools in Garissa County.

1.3.1 Specific Objective

1. To examine how leadership qualities of school managers influence implementation of strategic plans.
2. To determine how Resource allocation influence implementation of strategic plans.
3. To find out the influence of human resource capacity on the implementation of strategic plans.
4. To investigate the influence of school culture on the implementation of strategic plans.

1.3.2 Research question

1. What is the influence of leadership quality on implementation of strategic plans?
2. What is the influence of resource allocation on the implementation of strategic plans?
3. What is the influence of human resource capacity on implementation of strategic plans?
4. What is the influence of school culture on the implementation of strategic plans?

1.4 Theoretical Background

1.4.1 Five-Model System for Strategy Implementation

Bourgeois and Brodwin (1984) created a five-model system for strategy implementation categorizing strategy implementation practices. It shows different positions or viewpoints one might assume while implementing strategy; the commander model draws its influences from the military life, in the sense that the CEO wields absolute power. In this model the CEO is the rational agent behind the strategy decisions and plays no role in implementation. The CEO-model's works best with a powerful executive with few personal biases and vast and accurate sources of information.

The organizational change model is based on planned interventions in the organization's structure and systems, which sets off the desired behavioural outcomes. The model deals with strategy implementation and emphasizes how organizational structure, incentive compensation and control Systems can be used to facilitate the execution of a strategy. The CEO applies behavioural science techniques to manipulate his organization into compliance with his strategic plan. It employs several techniques for successful implementation such as using the structure and Staffing to effectively convey the firm's new priorities and focus attention on the desired areas, changing the Systems used for planning, performance measurement and incentive compensation and using cultural adaptation techniques to introduce system-wide change.

The collaborative model extends the power of strategic decision-making from the CEO to the organization's management team. The CEO makes use of group dynamics and brainstorming techniques so that managers with differing opinions can air their views during the strategic decision making process. According to this model the role of the CEO is that of a co-coordinator who facilitates the interaction among the decision makers resulting in the acceptance of all good ideas. This model helps to motivate the managers and also provides the strategic decision making process with more information and cognitive capital.

The cultural model is based on moulding the organization's culture to ensure the acceptance of a shared vision. The CEO guides the organization by communicating and instilling his vision and allowing the staff members to participate in designing their work procedures in tune with that vision. The role of the CEO is that of a coach who encourages staff members to take decisions in order to determine the operating details of executing the plan. This model is based on all organizational members' participating in decision making directed to perpetuate the vision.

The crevice model the strategic decisions are created bottom up by the organization's members and the role of the CEO is to act as judge and premise-setter and ensure an organizational context (structure, systems and culture) that will promote openness and innovation. This model suggests that the CEOs of large divisionalized firms should generate and implement strategies that maintain an open attitude to new information, use a general strategy to guide the firm, encourage bottom-up strategy formulation by making necessary changes in the systems and structures, intervene in the logical incrementalism (Quinn, 1980) manner and change structure and staff for minimizing aberrations. The crevice model offers a rather tempting standpoint from an

organization psychological perspective. It offers to make full use of the organizational members' knowledge and effort in the strategy process, encouraging participation.

1.4.2 Resource Base View Theory

Resources may be defined as the tangible and intangible assets a firm uses to choose and implement its strategies (Wang, 2009). According to resource-based theory, resources are generally classified as tangible or intangible (Galbreath, 2005) from which the latter can be categorized into assets and skills (capabilities).

The resource-based view (R.B.V) of the firm was introduced by (Wernerfelt, 1984; Barney, 1991). This approach affirms that the main sources of sustainable competitive advantage reside in the development and use of valuable firm's resources and capabilities. Tangible resources and capabilities include financial, physical, technological, and organizational, whereas intangible resources include humans, innovation, and reputation (Barney, 1991). This view focuses on the value (V), rarity (R), imitability (I), and organizational (O) aspects of resources and capabilities leading to a VRIO framework for gaining and sustaining competitive advantage. According to this framework only value-adding processes lead to competitive advantage, whereas non-value-adding capabilities may lead to competitive disadvantage as they distract resources unnecessarily. Rarity concerns the competitive advantage to be derived from having a service or product that few others have. Imitability is derived when competitors are unable to copy or replicate a service or product and may also refer to the knowledge capital of individual employees.

1.5 Empirical Literature Review

1.5.1 Leadership Quality

Leadership is the art and science of organizing a group of people and influencing their activities to achieve a common goal. Okumbe (1999) stated that the functions of the school managers are to provide assurance that policies and goals are formulated and that the methods are determined for the achievement of the stated objectives.

The management of Education in Kenya is guided by the Education Act of 1968 (revised in 1980). The Act gives the BoG powers to manage education at the school level. The BoG is conferred with the responsibility of management of public secondary schools and training institutions. They are responsible for promotion of quality education in school, protection of all movable and non-movable properties of the school and ensure security of school shares, funds and grants. Caldwell & Spinks (1988) note that, effective leadership creates effective schools. In Kenya secondary school leadership is vested on principals and board of governors. Their leadership effectiveness largely determines the quality of teaching and learning that take place.

According to Sushila (2004), a principal should be decisive, pleasant, strong, compassionate and understanding. He should however listen to other people's ideas and suggestions. Jacobus (2005) adds, a secondary school principal as a leader must get things done in and outside the school. He should be a democratic leader who does not limit others, should not be opposed to change, should welcome cooperation and be

selfless. Motivation is important in management and leadership because it ensures organizational goal attainment. Staff members can be motivated by being involved in decision making, by enhancing effective communication and by being recognized.

1.5.2 Resource Allocation

Resources may be defined as the tangible and intangible assets a firm uses to choose and implement its strategies (Wang, 2009). The availability of resources in terms of staff, skills, knowledge, finance and time, is thought to be a crucial part of strategy implementation (Alexander, 1985; Miller, 2002). Resources in essence represent the strengths that firms can use to assist with the conception and implementation strategies (Barney, 1991).

According to Ibukun (2010) resources such as man (teachers, policy makers, non-teaching staff); money (cash, cheque and notes); materials (raw materials, teaching and research materials, teaching aids and other equipment); management (policies, plans, programmes, time table); time and information are limited in supply and serve as input into the educational system.

Educational resources have been classified into four groups and include (a) physical resources such as school plants, classrooms, offices, recreational facilities and the entire school ground; (b) material resources including instructional aides, stationeries, education plans, objectives and prescribed methodologies; (c) human resources (both teaching and non-teaching staff); and (d) financial resources

According to Ngware, Wamukuru and Odebero (2006) the quality and adequacy of resources such as physical facilities, equipment, teaching and learning materials, all have a direct bearing on quality as they determine how effectively the curriculum is implemented. Saitoti, (2003) states that the major determinants of quality education include curriculum content, relevant instructional materials and equipment, physical facilities, a conducive learning environment, the quality of teaching force, and assessment and monitoring of learning achievements.

1.5.3 Human Resource Capacity

Kennedy (2005) defines staff development as a set of activities planned and carried out to promote the personal growth of teachers. Capacity building encompasses the country's human, scientific, technological, organizational, institutional and resource capabilities.

According to Cole and Southworth (2005), staff professional development includes those processes that improve the job-related knowledge, skills and attitudes of teachers. They continue to describe staff development as the process that is designed to positively influence knowledge, skills and attitudes of teachers in an attempt to help them improve the learning of students. On human resources, first the plan argues that in order to enhance quality management in secondary schools, it is imperative to have a well-qualified and highly motivated teaching force capable of understanding the needs of learners and the curriculum.

1.5.4 School Culture

Owens (1995) and Tagiuri (1968) define school culture as the values, beliefs, norms and behaviour patterns of the people who are members of the school community. School culture generally refers to a set of values and belief systems of various groups within the school. Deal and Peterson (1990) describe school culture as the unwritten rules, traditions, norms and expectations that seem to permeate everything: the way people act, how they dress, what they talk about or avoid talking about, their work, and their students. Schein (1985) also defines school culture as complex webs of traditions and rituals that have been built over time as teachers, students, parents, and administrators work together and demonstrate team work spirit when deal with crises and accomplishments.

2. Conceptual Framework

Conceptual framework is a set of broad ideas and principles taken from relevant fields enquiring how to structure a subsequent presentation (Reichel & Ramey, 2007). The conceptual framework for this study was issues that influence implementation of strategic plans in public secondary schools. The independent variable was issues that influence implementation of strategic plans that contains leadership quality, resources allocation, Human resource capacity and school culture while implementation of strategic plans will be the dependent variable. The independent variable which is the predicator influenced the dependent variable the (predicted variable) and the resultant outcome would be academic excellence, improved discipline, land and infrastructure development, stakeholder satisfaction and financial stability. The figure below demonstrates the relationship of the variables.

Source: Researcher 2015.

Figure1.1: Conceptual Framework

3. Methodology

The research design for this study was descriptive survey. The targeted population for the study comprised of 282 teachers, 338 members of Board of Governors and 27 Principals making a total population of 647 persons. The study adopted stratified sampling for teachers and BoG member's stratum using 10% of the targeted population while the Census method was applied to select the school principals who in this case became automatic respondents. Therefore, using the stratified random sampling design, the researcher selected a sample size of 28 teachers and 34 BoG members while the 27 principals were selected using census technique. Census method was appropriate for the principal as the respondents were less than 30. The study also used secondary sources of data from published progress reports, policy documents of the ministry of education and other stakeholders.

The researcher used questionnaires to get information from the BoG members, principals and teachers. Both structured and unstructured questions were used. In order to further enrich the data, Likert type questions were applied in some items. The study collected and analysed both qualitative and quantitative data. Quantitative data was analysed using descriptive statistics with interpretations giving frequencies, percentages and mean scores. For qualitative data; content analysis was used to analyse the responses.

The researcher used content validity to examine whether the instruments answered the research questions. The study used a representative sample of 30 out of 208 of the managers of the 6 secondary schools.

The study used test – retest method which involves administering the same scale or measure to the same group of respondents at two separate times. Test of reliability was carried out to check on the internal consistency of data measurement instrument.

3. Research Findings

The findings are presented according to the research objectives of the study and the research questions were used for the discussions of the findings. The results were presented in frequency tables, percentages and using graphs. Qualitative data was categorized into themes and the major themes discussed and reported. The study involved a total of 22 schools in which two (9.1%) of them were categorized as national schools, three (13.6%) of them were county school and the remaining 17 (77.3%) were sub-county schools.

A total of 27 schools were considered, giving rise to a sample size of 27 principals, while 10% of all teachers in the schools and 10% of BoG members were selected for the study and issued with questionnaires. The overall response rate was 77.5%. The study had a total sample of 69 respondents out of the 89 initially sampled, which represents 77.5% response rate.

The answer to this question was sought at two levels. First, the study sought to determine the existence of strategic plans in the studied schools and how such plans

were arrived at and implemented. The study found that not all schools had strategic plans, as depicted in the following figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1: Proportion of Schools with/without Strategic Plans

It is observed that 86% of the schools studied had strategic plans while the remaining 14% did not have any. It was also found that the principals participated in the development of the strategic plans in 90.9% (20 schools) but in 9.1% of them, the principal was not involved in strategic plan development. Further, the respondents gave different proportion of implementation levels of the strategic plans. The following figure 4.2 shows the proportion to which the strategic plans had been implemented among the 20 schools that had strategic plans.

Figure 4.2: Proportion of Strategic Plans Implemented

It is observed that 45% of schools had implemented 0 to 25% of their strategic plan, 41% had implemented 51 to 75% of their strategic plan while 14% of the respondents could not tell the proportion of the strategic plan so far implemented.

A number of challenges were found to be affecting the implementation of strategic plans. These included such factors like lack of funds, lack of commitment from stakeholders, political interference and security.

Table 4.6: Challenges Affecting Implementation of Strategic Plans

Challenge	Proportion of respondents (n = 20)	
	Number	Percentage
Lack of funding	15	75
Lack of commitment from the stakeholders	9	45
Political interference	6	30
Security	3	15

It is observed that the greatest challenge facing implementation of strategic plans is lack of funds. This sentiment was expressed by 75% of the respondents whose schools had strategic plans. The factor was followed by lack of commitment by stakeholders involved in the strategic plan, a factor that was identified by 45% of the respondents. Political interference was found to be a challenge facing strategic plan implementation, as expressed by 30% of the respondents. A relatively small proportion (15%) of respondents identified security as a challenge facing the implementation of strategic plans in schools.

4. Research Questions

a. What is the Influence of Leadership Quality on Implementation of Strategic Plans?

The study investigated the effect of leadership on the implementation of strategic plans. To achieve this, a series of questions were posed to the respondents.

Table 4.7: Responsibility for Strategic Plan Implementation

Person responsible	Respondents' views					
	Principals (n = 22)		Bog members (n = 25)		Teachers (n = 22)	
	No	%	No	%	No	%
Principal	12	54.5	12	48	3	13.6
Teachers	9	40.9	3	12	6	27.2
Stakeholders	21	95.4	15	60	15	68.2

It was noted that all respondents agreed that stakeholders are responsible for the implementation of strategic plans in schools. This opinion was expressed by the highest proportion of respondents in each category, with 95.4% of principals choosing this option, 60% of BoG members choosing it while 68.2% of teachers agreeing with the view. This view was followed in importance with the view that principals are responsible for strategic plan implementation. The sentiment was expressed by 54.5% of principals themselves, 48% of BoG members and 13.6% of teachers. The group that was viewed to be least responsible for the implementation of strategic plans was teachers,

who were identified by 40.9% of principals, 12% of BoG members and 27.2% of teachers themselves.

Table 4.8: Views on Influence of Stakeholders on Implementation of Strategic Plans

Level of influence	Respondents' views					
	Principals		Bog members		Teachers	
	No	%	No	%	No	%
Very high	17	77.3	5	22.7	3	13.6
High	5	22.7	17	77.3	19	86.4
Neither high nor low	-	-	-	-	-	-
Low	-	-	-	-	-	-
Very low	-	-	-	-	-	-

The BoG believe that principals have a very high influence on implementation of strategic plans; the BoG members have a high influence while teachers have low influence on the implementation of school strategic plans. This is in view of the fact that 60% of the BoG members viewed principals as having very high influence, 64% of them viewed themselves (BoG members) as having high influence while 48% of the BoG members viewed teachers as having low influence on the implementation of strategic plans. Only 36% of this category of respondents viewed teachers as having high influence on the implementation of strategic plans.

The study then sought teachers' views on the influence of each of the three stakeholders on the implementation of strategic plans. Their responses are portrayed in the following Table 4.10.

Table 4.10: Teachers' Views on Influence of Stakeholders on Implementation of Strategic Plans

Level of influence	Respondents' views (n = 22)					
	Principals		BoG members		Teachers	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
Very high	12	54.5	6	27.3	3	13.6
High	6	27.3	12	54.5	15	68.2
Neither high nor low	-	-	-	-	3	13.6
Low	-	-	3	13.6	-	-
Very low	3	13.6	-	-	-	-

From the preceding analysis, it is clear that the influence of the principals in the implementation is recognized by all respondents as being very high. This finding is in agreement with the view expressed by Sushila (2004), who avers that a principal should be a leader. He should be decisive, pleasant, strong, compassionate and understanding. It is also clear that the influence of the members of the BoG is viewed to be high. However, there is a difference in the understanding of the influence of teachers on the implementation of strategic plans. While principals believe that teachers have high influence, most of the members of the BoG believe that teachers' influence is low, yet teachers are the main implementers of all strategies involving academic programmes.

b. What is the Influence of Resource Allocation on the Implementation of Strategic Plans?

The second research question was: What is the influence of resource allocation on the implementation of strategic plans? This question was posed to all categories of respondents, including the principals, the BoG members and the teachers. To get answers to this question, the respondents were asked about the availability of various resources in their schools. Their responses are presented in the following Table 4.11.

Table 4.11: Availability of Various Resources for Strategic Plan Implementation

Resource type	Respondents' views											
	Principals (n = 22)				Bog members (n = 25)				Teachers (n = 22)			
	Yes		No		Yes		No		Yes		No	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
General resources	5	22.7	17	77.3	7	28	18	72	0	0	22	100
Financial resources	3	13.6	19	86.4	0	00	25	100	0	0	22	100
Budgeting	22	100	0	00	13	52	12	48	16	72.7	6	27.3
Physical resources	5	22.7	17	77.3	4	16	21	84	0	0	22	100

The findings indicated that 77.3% of principals were of the view that there are no general resources, 72% of members of boards of governors agreed with them while all teachers agreed that there are no resources for implementing strategic plans. Likewise, 86.4% of principals were of the view that there are never enough financial resources to implement strategic plans. This view was supported by all members of the BoG as well as all teachers. 77.3% of principals agreed that there are no enough physical resources. This sentiment was supported by 84% of members of BoG and all teachers. It therefore follows that in all schools, there are never enough physical structures to support implementation of strategic plans. This finding agrees with the finding by Ibukun (2010), who says that resources are always limited in supply in schools.

With regard to budgeting, all principals agreed that they prepare budgets for their schools. However, only 52% of members of BoG agreed that budgeting is conducted in their schools while 48% disagreed.

The study also sought the level of availability of physical facilities in the schools studied. The facilities studied included the availability classrooms, library, laboratory, dormitory, staffroom, land, text books, washrooms and sources of water. The following Table 4.13 to 4.15 shows the level of availability of the said physical resources according to different respondent categories.

Table 4.13: Principals' Views on the Level of Adequacy of Physical Resource

Resource type	Principals' views (n = 22)									
	Very adequate		Adequate		Fairly adequate		Inadequate			
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Classrooms	3	13.6	8	36.4	11	50	-	-	-	-
Library	-	-	3	13.6	3	13.6	16	72.7	-	-
Laboratories	3	13.6	5	22.7	6	27.3	8	36.4	-	-
Dormitories	3	13.6	3	13.6	10	45.5	6	27.3	-	-

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Staffrooms	-	-	3	13.6	10	45.5	9	40.9
Land	9	40.9	4	18.2	9	40.9	-	-
Text books	3	13.6	7	31.8	12	54.5	-	-
Washrooms	3	13.6	3	13.6	12	54.5	6	27.3
Source of water	6	27.3	3	13.6	10	45.5	3	13.6

It is observed that land, text books and classrooms are the most adequate physical resources, according to the principals. The most adequate of these resources was land since nearly 60% of the respondents held the view that it was either very adequate or just adequate. None of the responses suggested that it was inadequate. This was followed by classrooms, in which 50% of the respondents believed that it was either very adequate or just adequate. Text books, on the other hand were said to be very adequate or adequate by 45.5% of the respondents but none viewed them as being inadequate.

Library was the least adequate of the physical resources. This is because a whopping 72.7% of the respondents reported it to be inadequate while only 13.6% viewed it as adequate and a similar percentage viewed it as being fairly adequate. None of the respondents viewed the library as being very adequate. The library was followed in inadequacy by staffrooms. Staffroom was identified by 40.9% as being inadequate while 45.5% viewed it as being fairly adequate. Only 13.6% of the respondents viewed it as being adequate but none viewed it as being very adequate. The rest of the facilities can be said to be fairly adequate there is near parity on the respondents who believed that they were adequate or inadequate, while most of the respondents held the view that the resources were fairly adequate.

c. What is the Influence of Human Resource Capacity on Implementation of Strategic Plans?

Table 4.18: Influence of Human Resource Capacity on Implementation of Strategic Plans

Aspect of concern	Principals (n = 22)				Teachers (n = 22)			
	Yes		No		Yes		No	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Training in strategic management	19	86.4	3	13.6	6	27.3	16	72.7
Strategic planning training	8	36.4	14	63.6	9	40.9	13	59.1
Improvement on service delivery	19	86.4	3	13.6	8	36.4	14	63.6

From Table 4.18, it is evident that a few of the respondents had acquired capacity building on strategic management or strategic planning training. From the table, it is observed that nearly all principals, ideally 86.4% of them, had undergone training on strategic management. Only 13.6% of them had not undergone the training. However, only 27.3% of the teachers had undergone training in strategic management while 72.7% had not. From the above analysis, it is evident that majority of the principals have the requisite capacity in strategic management, but only a small proportion of them have

knowledge in strategic planning. Very few teachers have strategic management training or strategic planning.

On enquiring whether the acquired knowledge has improved their service delivery, all principals with this knowledge (86.4%) responded in the affirmative while some of the teachers disagreed, with only 36.4% as opposed to the earlier 40.9% agreeing that the knowledge had improved their service delivery.

From this analysis, it is clear that, as much as principals are crucial in the implementation of strategic plans in schools, majority of them do not have the requisite training strategic planning as only 36.4% of the principals studied had this knowledge. While a relatively large proportion of 86.4% have knowledge in strategic planning, many of them only acquired the knowledge as a unit in college before they became principals, hence could not critically focus on the duty at hand. The teachers' situation is even worse as most of them neither have training in strategic management nor strategic planning. This finding is in conformity with the report by Republic of Kenya, (2005), which said that many secondary school head teachers had not been adequately trained in management and administration and were ineffective and lacking in accountability.

d. What is the Influence of School Culture on the Implementation of Strategic Plans?

Influence of School Culture on Implementation of Strategic Plans

The fourth research question was: What is the influence of school culture on the implementation of strategic plans? This question was posed to all respondents. The answer to the question was sought through finding out the presence of school mission, vision and values that was guiding on the implementation of strategic plans. The following Table 4.19 portrays the results of this enquiry.

Table 4.19: Influence of school culture on the strategic plans

Culture aspect	Respondents' views											
	Principals (n = 22)				Bog members (n = 25)				Teachers (n = 22)			
	Yes		No		Yes		No		Yes		No	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Mission and vision	22	100	0	0	25	100	0	0	18	81.8	4	18.2
Values	22	100	0	0	25	100	0	0	22	100	0	00

It is observed that most of the schools studied had mission and vision and values guiding on strategic plan implementation. All principals agreed that their schools had mission and vision, all members of BoG agreed with them while 81.8% of the teachers agreed that their schools had vision and mission. There was agreement among all the respondents that all the schools studied had values. It can therefore be concluded that all schools have values that they strive to attain.

The study finally sought the influence of school culture on the implementation of school strategic plans. This was sought by asking the respondents to state the extent to which they thought various culture aspects affected the implementation of strategic

plans in their schools. The following shows the response of principals regarding this aspect.

Table 4.20: Principals' Views on aspects Influencing Implementation of Strategic Plans

Stakeholder	Principals' views (n = 22)									
	SA		A		U		D		SD	
	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%
Existence of clear vision	6	27.3	13	59.1	-	-	-	-	3	13.6
Ownership by management	5	22.7	11	50	3	13.6	-	-	3	13.6
Existence of team work spirit	6	27.3	14	63.6	-	-	-	-	2	9.1
Role division	3	13.6	15	68.2	-	-	4	18.2	-	-
Discipline	-	-	15	68.2	-	-	7	31.8	-	-

From Table 4.20, it is observed that according to the principals, role division, existence of team work and existence of clear vision has paramount influence on implementation of school strategic plan. This is in view of the fact that well over 80% of the principals either agreed or strongly disagreed that these aspects greatly influence implementation of strategic plans. The only aspects that did not get such overwhelming support from principals were ownership by management that was supported by a total of 72.2% of the principals who either agreed or disagreed, and discipline. The influence of discipline on implementation of strategic plans was supported by 68.2% of principals who agreed that it influences implementation of strategic plans, while 31.8% disagreed. From the above analysis, it is clear that role division, existence of team work spirit, existence of clear vision, discipline and ownership by management all have major influences on the implementation of strategic plans. The finding is in line with Schein (1985) who defined school culture as complex webs of traditions and rituals that have been built over time as teachers, students, parents, and administrators work together and demonstrate team work spirit when dealing with crises and accomplishments.

Subjected to the same variables above, members of the BoG had a more or less similar view to that given by the principals as they tended to agree with most of the aspects described. Their views are presented in the following Table 4.21.

Table 4.21: BoG Members' Views on Aspects Influencing Implementation of Strategic Plans

Stakeholder	BoG Members' views (n = 25)									
	SA		A		U		D		SD	
	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%
Existence of clear vision	8	32	12	48	-	-	5	20	-	-
Ownership by management	-	-	20	80	-	-	5	20	-	-
Existence of team work spirit	4	16	16	64	5	20	-	-	-	-
Role division	-	-	10	40	11	44	4	16	-	-
Discipline	-	-	16	64	-	-	9	36	-	-

From Table 4.21, it is observed that 80% of the BoG members either strongly agreed or just agreed that existence of team work spirit, ownership by management and existence of clear vision have great influence on implementation of strategic plans. Discipline also

has major influence on implementation of strategic plans since 64% of the BoG members agreed that it influences strategic plan implementation. The only aspect that did not receive much support was role division, which had only 50% of the respondents agreeing with. However, most of the remaining respondents were undecided about its influence, while only 16% disagreed about its influence. It therefore follows that most of the respondents actually agreed that the aspect influences the implementation of strategic plan.

The teachers' view on the influence of the same aspects on the implementation of strategic plans in schools revealed that most of the teachers believed that all the aspects had great influence. Table 4.22 below depicts their responses on this aspect.

Table 4.22: Teachers' Views on Aspects Influencing Implementation of Strategic Plans

Stakeholder	Teachers' views (n = 22)									
	SA		A		U		D		SD	
	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%
Existence of clear vision	-	-	19	86.4	-	-	-	-	3	13.6
Ownership by management	-	-	22	100	-	-	-	-	-	-
Existence of team work spirit	-	-	19	86.4	-	-	-	-	3	13.6
Role division	-	-	19	86.4	-	-	-	-	-	-
Discipline	3	13.6	19	86.4	-	-	-	-	-	-

From Table 4.22, it is clear that almost all respondents of this category (teachers agreed that all the given aspects influenced the implementation of strategic plans. From the table, more than 80% of the respondents agreed that all the aspects influenced the implementation of strategic plans. However, all the respondents agreed ownership by management influences the implementation of strategic plans. Thus, there is an overwhelming agreement by these respondents that aspects given influence the implementation of strategic plans.

5. Summary, Conclusion and Recommendation

5.1 Summary of the Findings

- a) Most of the schools studied have strategic plans that determine what they intend to do within specified period and the activities they plan to do in order to achieve the objectives of the strategic plan.
- b) As much as the schools have elaborate strategic plans, implementation of the plans has been a problem. Many of the schools studied had implemented only 25% of the plans, leaving a very large portion not yet implemented.
- c) The implementation of strategic plans in schools is faced with challenges such as lack of funds, lack of commitment from stakeholders, political interference and to some extent, security. Of these challenges, lack of funds is the most prevalent challenge affecting implementation of strategic plans.

- d) The principal, teachers and other stakeholders are all responsible for the implementation of strategic plans in schools. The principal is recognized as the leading figure in the implementation of strategic plans in schools.
- e) Most schools lack both the financial and physical resources, a factor that greatly hampers implementation of strategic plans.
- f) All schools prepare budgets for their operations, as evidenced by the principals and teachers.
- g) Most schools have only two sources of funds – school fees and grants from the government. Of these, funds from school fees are the most important as all schools are assured of the fees as long as there are students. None of the schools studied had any income generating activities organized by the school.
- h) Land is the only resource that all schools studied seemed to have in abundance. All respondents identified land as being either adequate or very adequate for the schools studied. However, there was no evidence of the use of the land for income as none of the schools had any income generating activity.
- i) Most of the schools lack libraries, wash rooms and sources of water. However, there was no shortage of classrooms, staffrooms or dormitories. Text books were fairly adequate in most of the schools studied.
- j) Experts, parents and members of the local community play very little roles in the implementation of strategic plans in schools.
- k) The training in strategic management acquired by the principals was found to have assisted in improving service delivery to a majority of the principals, with only 13.6% who did not believe that the training had helped them improve service delivery.
- l) All schools studied had school mission, vision and values that guide them through the implementation of strategic plans.
- m) School culture influences implementation of school strategic plans. All respondents were in agreement that school culture aspects like the existence of clear vision, ownership by management, existence of team work spirit, role division and discipline have profound influence on the implementation of school strategic plans.

5.2 Recommendations

5.2.1 Policy Recommendations

In view of the study findings and conclusions outlined in the previous sections, the following recommendations are made from the study:

- a) Schools should diversify on their sources of funding as this has great effects on the implementation of strategic plans. However, most schools only relied on school fees as the main source of funds and government grants whose time of arrival is not definite.
- b) Implementation of school strategic plans cannot be a one man show as it requires input from various stakeholders. As such, all relevant stakeholders should cooperate in order to successfully implement school strategic plans.

- c) Schools should come up with means and ways of utilizing the vast land that is currently lying idle. Though growing of fodder and other common fruits and vegetables are examples of possible land use.
- d) Principals should seek training in strategic planning and management. Most principals studied had knowledge in strategic management acquired as a unit while at college, but lacked the strategic planning aspect. For effective implementation of school strategic plans, the principal as the lead implementer should have vast knowledge in the area.
- e) Schools should organize training on strategic management and planning for teachers so as to acquaint them with the necessary skills in the implementation of strategic plans. Very few teachers have such knowledge yet they take part in the implementation of school strategic plans.
- f) Schools should establish specific culture aspects to guide them in the implementation of strategic plans as these cultures help in orienting the workers towards activities geared towards the implementation of school strategic plans.

5.2.2 Recommendation for Further Research

This study was conducted in secondary schools in only one county out of the 47 counties in Kenya. The findings from the study may not therefore be generalized for the rest of the counties as the sample of counties is relatively small. It is therefore recommended that a similar study be conducted in at least ten other counties spread all over the country in order to make the findings more generalizable to the rest of the counties.

5.3 Conclusion

From the study findings, it is evident that most secondary schools prepare strategic plans and actually attempt to implement them. However, the implementation of the strategies is affected by a number of factors, key among them being finances. Within the schools, the principal is the key personnel with the greatest influence on the implementation of strategic plans, though other personnel like teachers and boards of governors cannot be ignored. The Ministry of Education is main external stakeholder with influence on the implementation of strategic plans. For effective implementation of strategic plans, there is need to harmonize the operations of both internal and external stakeholders. Situations in which an important player like the BoG not knowing or recognizing the role of key partners like teachers in the implementation process are bound to slow down implementation of the plans and should be avoided as much as possible.

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